

8T – Manifold Automorphisms

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Abstract:

By analyzing the general idea behind the framework of varying curvature, it is possible to put the major equations describing Fermions and Bosons as a result of a more general principle, which is object automorphism, in particular manifold automorphism, which is synonymous with self-variance. The Fermionic and Bosonic configurations at spatial and temporal coordinate are direct results of variations of the object.

Introduction

The main ideas of the 8T framework can be put in concise way using just the main equation. This equation describe the varying manifold which is part of the packet of manifolds of the same class. Those manifolds has areas which are highly curved and isomorphic to acceleration from those areas. Let M_E denote the Einstein manifold, while the subscript is indexing the manifolds itself.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_m}{\partial t_m} \delta g_m - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial t_n} \delta g_n = 0$$

$$1 \leq m, n < k/2$$

Such that that the original form of the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Fermions were proven to be arbitrary variations of the manifolds, which are vanishing curvature spikes. The idea of Fermions can be put in rigor using an Iso-arrow from the manifold self-variation to the manifold.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

$$\psi: (M_E, g) \rightarrow (M_E, g)$$

That is to state that the manifold image after the arrow operation is the same manifold with additional constant, which is N size, and represent a certain number of elements which no curvature da facto. The Bosons are generated from the state of the additional arrow, which is synonymous with theorem two. Once a pair satisfying a certain condition, i.e. being two and three devisable, a Boson can be propagated. i denote the number of primes in the N -tuple. For simplicity sake the coupling constant presented prime pairs.

$$(P_1, P_2); i = 2$$

$$[2,3] \sum_{i=1}^{i=2} P_i \Rightarrow True$$

The Bosonic arrow is a continuation of the previous arrow of Fermions vanishing into matter, or the automorphism of the Lorentz manifold.

$$Y: (\psi: (M_E, g) \rightarrow (M_E, g)) \rightarrow (M_E, g)$$

The Bosonic arrow is again to the same manifold. This arrow however is indicating that there is some net curvature on the manifold, which rose from the original arrow. This arrow is a violation of the stationarity condition that causes Fermions to cluster. The Bosonic arrow is a continuation of the Fermion arrow, and can be executed if the condition above is fulfilled. It is possible to expend the beauty of arrows using another major idea of the 8T. That is the idea of manifold flattening each other via areas of extremum curvature. Each manifold pairs has inverse curvature orientation, the Flattening arrow is than in rigor:

$$\mathcal{F}: (M_E, g)^{i-1} \Leftrightarrow (M_E, -g)^i$$

$$1 \leq i \leq K;$$

$$K \in \mathbb{R}$$

Which is similar to the main equation. That arrow is the packet constructor, as it takes the inverse flows to zero, flattening each two manifolds.

$$\Lambda: [(M_E, g)^{i-1} \Leftrightarrow (M_E, -g)^i] \rightarrow 0$$

$$\Lambda: Y \rightarrow 0$$

$$(M_E, g)^{i-1} - (M_E, g)^i = 0$$

$$(M_E, g)^{i-1} = (M_E, g)^i$$

Summing up, those objects called manifolds can be put in two different kinds of arrows. The first class of arrows are automorphism arrows, from the manifold to the same manifold. Those arrows are the Fermion and Boson constructors. Those arrows **than** leading to areas of extremum curvatures, which invoke the second class of an arrows, interaction among manifolds at those areas, which lead to flatness as there exist acceleration from those areas, given by the main equation. It is important to emphasis that those are **dual classes** of arrows. Such that they are aligned in time. It could have put differently by saying that the interacting manifolds leading to flatness, is causing for the Fermions to appear in such way that no curvature is manifested **and then** Bosons are constructed. In other words, it is impossible to distinguish which condition come first, and it is not important for that matter. The whole 8T construction should be examined as one set of arrows, from the manifold to itself, and from manifold to complimentary manifolds in the packet.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8T – The Grand Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Ohad's Theory